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NEW SIGHTING OF THE NEAR THREATENED EURASIAN OTTER *Lutra lutra* IN TUNISIA

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Abstract

The Eurasian otter, Lutra lutra (Linnaeus, 1758), is the most widely distributed of the otter species and is listed as Near Threatened in the IUCN Red List. However, in Tunisia, information about its distribution remains poorly known. A new sighting of this species was made during an expedition near the shores of El Barrak's dam where a dead body and footprints were found. This sighting is a new record, 36 years after the last one by Macdonald and Mason.

Keywords: Otter; new sighting; Near Threatened; Tunisia; Africa.

INTRODUCTION

The Eurasian otter *Lutra lutra* is classified by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (**Roos et al., 2015**) as a Near Threatened species. The species has a wide distribution which covers Europe, most of Asia and North Africa. Although its populations are fairly well studied in Europe where they seem to be recovering (**Roos et al., 2015**), the North African populations are poorly investigated. In fact, over the last six decades only five scientific studies were carried out in three countries: Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia (**Macdonald and Mason 1983, 1984; Macdonald et al., 1985; Delibes et al. 2012; Badis et al. 2015**).

In Tunisia, **Macdonald & Mason (1983)** explained that the otter is common in the Northwest of the country and is quite abundant in the rivers of Oued Medjerda. Nevertheless, between 1983 and 2019, significant changes directly affected the streams in Northern Tunisia such as pollution (**Jdid et al., 1999; Abidi et al., 2015**) and dam construction (**Yadh et al. 2008**). No sighting of the species has been made since.

No national field survey has ever been undertaken in Tunisia and information on the status of the population of *Lutra lutra* is rare over the last 36 years, when the single study was made in the country (**Macdonald and Mason, 1982**). The aim of this study is to gather preliminary data about the remaining Tunisian population in order to comprehend its distribution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on the survey conducted by Macdonald & Mason in 1982, a team investigated 35 sites in which signs of otters were previously found (**Table 1**). The survey was conducted between 2017 and 2019. At each site a transect of 1.5 km was covered searching for spraints or footprints. Roads leading to these localities were carefully surveyed for possible dead otters as a result of a collision with vehicles whilst attempting to cross the road.

Table 1. List of visited sites in northern Tunisia from 2017 to 2019

Governorate	Station	Date
Jendouba	Eddir’s dam	19-XII-2017
Jendouba	Oued Selloul	28-VI-2018
Jendouba	Barrage Jwewdeya’s dam	28-VI-2018
Jendouba	Oued Bou Heurtma 1	11-XI-2018
Jendouba	Oued Bou Heurtma 2	11-XI-2018
Bizerte	Oued El Bagrat	26-XI-2017
Bizerte	Joumin	26-XI-2017
Bizerte	Sejnene	28-I-2018
Bizerte	Oued Ettin’s dam	18-II-2018
Bizerte	Oued Sejnene	22-IV-2018
Béja	Sidi El Barrak’s dam 1	18-II-2018
Béja	Chotte El Zweraa	21-IV-2018
Béja	Sidi El Barrak’s dam 2	21-IV-2018
Béja	Thibar’s dam	26-VII-2018
Béja	Hamem Essaiela	26-VII-2018
Nabeul	Oued Borj Cedreya	20-VIII-2018
Nabeul	Lebna’s dam	29-VIII-2018
Nabeul	Oued Lebna	11-IX-2018
Nabeul	Oued Lahjar 1	29-VIII-2018
Nabeul	Oued Tafakhsit	29-VIII-2018
Nabeul	Oued Abid	03-IX-2018
Nabeul	Oued Lahjar 2	06-IX-2018
Nabeul	Oued Chiba	07-IX-2018
Béja	Ouechtata	01-VI-2018
Jendouba	Sidi Rouin	04-II-2018
Jendouba	Oued Zen	04-II-2018
Jendouba	Ain Baya	08-IV-2018
Jendouba	Deren’s dam	08-IV-2018
Jendouba	Barbara’s dam	08-IV-2018
Jendouba	Sidi Said	08-IV-2018
Jendouba	Beni Mtir’s dam	25-VIII-2018
Jendouba	Oued Beni Mtir	25-VIII-2018
Jendouba	Beni Mtir	25-VIII-2018
Béja	Sidi El Barrak’s dam 3	26-II-2019
Béja	Nefza	26-II-2019
Total	35	3 years

RESULTS

At these 35 visited sites, signs of the presence of otters were observed at only two sites (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Map of sites visited and occurrence locations of the Eurasian otter in Northern Tunisia during the last three years

No direct sightings were made of otters but footprints were observed in two localities (El Barrak’s dam and Nefza). The abundance of these footprints was extremely high at Nefza with over 100 footprints all along a river bed leading to El Barrak’s dam. A dead otter was discovered on a road near the shores of El Barrak’s dam (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Dead body of the Eurasian otter found near El Barrak’s dam

Apparently, the otter was struck by a car while attempting to cross the roadway. Based on its body length, the specimen appears to be an adult. It was severely damaged and so it was not possible to determine the sex. The body was found at a distance of 5km from

the nearest footprint. These observations suggest the presence of an otter population surrounding the streams leading to El Barrak’s dam and clearly roads in that area represent a threat for the species.

DISCUSSION

The fieldwork focused on the Northern side of the Madjerda river where water is permanent compared to the Southern side of the river where water is scarce and the land starts to turn dry as it approaches the steppes of Kairouan.

The otter occurred strictly in the Northwest part of Tunisia where water is still available and clean. Habitat fragmentation in the Cap Bon (Northeast) region was very accentuated and the absence of otter footprints suggest that the isolated population that existed back in 1983 may have disappeared. Oued Abid, the main river stream in Cap Bon, is heavily affected by the industrial activities surrounding the area.

The otter population of Tunisia is of high importance as it lives on the edge of its geographical distribution. More research needs to be carried out with more emphasis on ecological protocols in order to study the otter’s distribution, habitat preferences and population dynamics in the region. This will also help to identify threats and enable the creation of an action plan to preserve the remaining population of this threatened species and its natural habitats in Tunisia. The fact that signs of the occurrence of the otter was only found in two localities out of all of the visited sites, and that there was also a dead body on the road, may indicate the threat of road networks on the remaining population of the Eurasian otter in Tunisia.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

ZAKHER BOURAGAOU is an evolutionary ecologist, mainly working on reptiles, specifically Lacertid lizards. He investigates their biology and ecology in Tunisia through various procedures from skeletochronology to species distribution modelling (SDM).

Wael Ben ABA is an entomologist who has the largest private collection of Coleoptera in Tunisia. He has worked with international museums on sampling unstudied invertebrates in Tunisia and participated in a project as lead entomologist to study the biodiversity of the Madjerda river.

CHAWKI NAJJAR is a wildlife veterinarian and ecologist. He worked with Marwell Wildlife on the population dynamics and ecological preferences of reintroduced antelopes (*Oryx*, *Addax*, *Gazelles*) and ostriches in the Southern national parks and on the ecology of Tunisian tortoises. He also worked on the evaluation of the ecological diversity of the national parks ecosystems, organised translocations and reintroductions of wild animals and gives technical advice to both managers and workers of national parks in breeding and monitoring endangered species.

FAOUZ KILANI is curator of the scientific collection and an evolutionary ecologist. She is a passionate field student dedicated to the study of the natural world and conservation.

She has just graduated after investigating the behaviour of scimitar-horned oryx in two national parks as part of one of a Marwell's conservation project.

GHASSEN KMIRA is an evolutionary ecologist who is very passionate about zoology and botany. He is particularly interested in terrestrial arthropods, and is studying the taxonomy and ecology of spiders for his Master's degree. He is one of the very few scientific illustrators in Tunisia and aspires to use this skill to raise awareness about protecting global biodiversity and popularising science.

OLFA SEHLI is an ecologist and marine biologist who studied marine ecology and biodiversity for her Master's degree. Olfa is working as a marine life conservationist in TAW, trying to know more about the Tunisian biodiversity and promote this knowledge to raise awareness. She is also passionate about documentary filmmaking and underwater photography.

SAHAR CHEBAANE is a marine biologist, especially non-indigenous species. She achieved her Master's research degree in marine biodiversity from the faculty of sciences of Sfax and Master's degree in ecology and environment with the University of Le Mans, France. During her internship she set up a monitoring programme for non-indigenous species in Monastir Bay and in the Kuriat islands MCPA.

HELA BOUGHDIRI is a second year Master's student in evolutionary ecology at the University of Tunis El Manar, and is passionate about zoology and especially reptiles. Her research focuses on the breeding strategy and behaviour of *Crocodylus niloticus* in captivity in Djerba Explore Park

MOHAMED SGHEIR BEN YOUSSEF is an amateur entomologist and wildlife photographer.

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MOHAMED AMINE HAMMOUDA is a documentary photographer and cinematographer with over five years of experience working with non-profit organisations in education, citizenship and human rights.

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A STUDY OF THE DIET AND DISTRIBUTION OF THE EURASIAN OTTER (*Lutra lutra*) IN THE WATER OF LEITH, EDINBURGH, SCOTLAND

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For the dissertation element of my MSc in Biodiversity, Wildlife and Ecosystem Health at the University of Edinburgh, I am undertaking a study into the diet and distribution of the Eurasian otter on a 12-mile urban stretch of the Water of Leith, Edinburgh, from Balerno to Leith. This is being done in conjunction with the Water of Leith Conservation Trust and the International Otter Survival Fund

Many studies have been undertaken on otters in coastal and riparian habitats (**Gallant, 2007**), but less is known of the movements of urban otters in the UK. As more reports